

DEMONSTRATION OF RISK-TAKING CHARACTERISTICS DURING STUDENT PERIOD

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the analysis of the characteristics of students' risk-taking, its psychological foundations, and the factors influencing it. Also, a number of socio-psychological studies conducted by foreign and Uzbek scientists on this problem are analyzed in detail. At the same time, the article presents the results of the research conducted by the authors, which sheds light on the relationship between students' risk-taking characteristics and age, gender, marital status, and sibling status.

Risk-taking is one of the important aspects of human personality, which expresses how much one is willing to accept uncertainty and risk in the decision-making process. The student period is considered an important stage in self-awareness, gaining life experience, seeking new opportunities, and learning to make independent decisions, and the risk-taking characteristic plays an important role in their personal development and success.

The issue of risk has been widely studied by foreign psychologists, and these studies have served to solve many scientific problems in the field of risk-prone behavioral characteristics and their measurement, prediction, and mathematical calculation of probable risky behavior. Risk is an interdisciplinary subject of research, and research has been conducted in this area from the perspective of various disciplines, including: psychology (O.S. Deyneka, A.J.T. Zhuravlev, Yu. Kozeletsky, D.V. Kolesov, T.V. Kornilova, M.A. Kotik, A.G. Niazashvili, B.A. Petrovsky, G.M.N.N Edwards, B. Fishhoff, L.B. Gratt, S. Lichtenstein, D. Kahneman, J.H. Kasperson, R.W. Kates, P. Slovic, A. Tversky, M. Zuckerman, etc.); sociology (A. Wildavsky, K.A. Gavrillov, M. Douglas, V.I. Zubkov, Yu.A. Zubok, S.A. Kravchenko, S.A. Krasikov, N. Luman, A.V. Brain, Kh.Zhi. Smakotina, O.N. Yanitsky, O. Renn, etc.); philosophy (V. Bek, Yu. L. Vorobyov, K. Marx, O. N. Mizinova, V. S. Solovyov, V. B. Ustyantsev, N. F. Fedorov, etc.) [1].

Russian psychologists have studied risk in several directions. Among them, E.N. Kiryanova [3] conducted research on the topic "Manifestations of risk in the activities of hazardous professions", in which the risk-taking behavior of specialists working in hazardous conditions was studied. The researcher emphasizes that the psychological state of people working in hazardous professions directly affects their ability to assess risk. The author makes the following recommendations to reduce the negative consequences of risk: 1) training and improving the skills of employees in physical and mental, emergency

preparedness, 2) providing them with constant psychological support, a healthy environment within the group, stress management and safety training.

The level of risk-taking tendency in adolescents and young adults was studied by Uzbek psychologist N.M. Mullabayeva [2]. The researcher noted that personal characteristics, social, emotional and psychological factors significantly affect risk-taking.

In our study, we used the "Risk Propensity Questionnaire" proposed by K. Levitin to study the characteristics of risk-taking in students. This questionnaire is designed to diagnose the level of risk-taking tendency. According to the results, 6% of students had a high level of risk, 33% had a slightly high level, 56% had a medium level, and 5% had a low level.

The results were examined for their association with the respondents' age, sibling status, marital status, and gender (Table 1). Pearson's correlation coefficient was used for this.

Table 1. Correlation of risk-taking behavior in students with other indicators

	Age	Marital status	Sibling status	Risk taking	Gender
Age	1				
Marital status	0,52**	1			
Sibling status	0,03	0,02	1		
Risk taking	-0,14	0,04	0,15	1	
Gender	-0,10	0,25	-0,18	0,57***	1

Note: ** $p \leq 0,05$; *** $p \leq 0,01$.

According to the results of the risk-taking questionnaire, it was found that the risk-taking trait in students depends on gender (stronger in men), but does not depend on age, marital status, and sibling status (number of children in the family).

The correlation between risk-taking and age (-0.14) is a statistically insignificant indicator. This means that age does not affect the formation of risk-taking during the student period.

The insignificant effect of sibling status on risk-taking can be explained as follows: the number of children in a person's family certainly forms certain psychological characteristics in him, but it is not the only factor affecting risk-taking. In the analysis of sibling status, the number of children in the family is also important. If there are 2 children in a family, both the older and younger children can grow up in the same conditions. If there are 5-6 children, older children are more responsible, and younger children are more likely to be freer. In summary, risk-taking is a measure of a person's willingness to accept uncertainty and risk in the decision-making process, and is related to personal characteristics, social, emotional and psychological factors, and gender characteristics.

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